

Meducide: Reframing and naming the destruction of medical education in armed conflict zones

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Background and rationale

Historical and current crises taught us how armed conflicts destroy far more than physical infrastructure such as buildings and borders. It also destroys knowledge capital and social infrastructure through which communities produce knowledge, build professional capacities, and shape public wellbeing. In recent years, critical scholarship has used concepts such as “scholasticide” (United Nations Human Rights Office of the High Commissioner, 2024) and Educide to describe the systematic massive destruction of educational systems (human and physical/environmental) during wars and armed conflicts (Alousi, 2022; Iriqat et al., 2025). These concepts are significantly important because they exceed the incidental “damage” and offer analysis toward the recognition that education itself is intentionally targeted as part of wider strategies of weakening communities, dispossession, and social fragmentation. Although medical education is a major force in shaping communities’ health, their future public health and well-being, it has often been subsumed within the broader destruction of higher education.

Medical schools occupy a unique position at the intersection of education, healthcare, and state capacity. They are not only sites of teaching and assessment, but also institutions tied to teaching hospitals, clinical supervision, professional regulation, research, and the long-term production of the health workforce (Barnett-Vanes, 2016). When a medical school is destroyed, occupied, looted, or rendered non-functional, the consequences extend beyond the interruption of academic learning. The damage reverberates through clinical training pipelines, licensing exams and systems, specialist formation, and ultimately the capacity of societies to care for wounded, displaced, and chronically ill populations. In fragile and conflict-affected contexts, where health workforce shortages are already severe, such disruption intensifies long-term health inequities and weakens prospects for recovery (Boniol et al., 2022; Haakenstad et al., 2022).

This concept note proposes **Meducide (M[edical]edu[cation]cide)** as a term for naming and analyzing this specific form of systematic and massive destruction. Inspired by wider debates on the destruction of schooling and education reflected in the concept of Educide, and scholasticide, Meducide calls for special attention to the systematic dismantling all medical education systems during armed conflict. It argues that attacks on medical education should not be treated as a secondary educational concern or subsumed within broad reports, but as a critical public health, human rights, and post-conflict reconstruction issue.

Defining Meducide

In this note, I offer defining Meducide as the systematic and intentional destruction, dismantling, and incapacitation of medical education systems during armed conflicts and political violence, resulting in long-term harm to health-system capacity, public health and population wellbeing. This definition deliberately extends beyond the bombing of campuses or the closure of universities. It includes the destruction of teaching hospitals, the loss of laboratories and libraries, the interruption of clinical placements, the fragmentation of accreditation and licensing systems, the displacement or

killing of students and faculty, and the breakdown of the institutional and psychosocial conditions required for medical and health professional formation.

Meducide as a concept is needed because broader terms such as Educide, while analytically very valuable, do not fully capture the distinctive role of medical education. The destruction of a general school system undoubtedly has devastating long-term social consequences. However, the destruction of medical education has an additional and immediate effect: it simultaneously undermines current healthcare provision and future healthcare capacity. Medical students are learners, but they are also future doctors; teaching hospitals are educational sites, but they are also essential care institutions; and faculty are academics, but also clinicians, mentors, and supervisors responsible for maintaining standards of safe practice (Barnett-Vanes et al., 2016; Dobiesz et al., 2022).

Meducide is therefore best understood through the lens of structural violence, in which harm is produced not only by direct physical attack, but also by social and political conditions that prevent populations from seeking basic needs. In this sense, Meducide is not simply the visible destruction of infrastructure. It is also the slower erosion of accreditation, governance, faculty pipelines, research capacity, and clinical competence. I.e., its destruction eliminates populations by depriving them from access to health, care, recovery and rehabilitation. Its effects accumulate over time and often remain visible far long after active warfare has ended, continuing into the peacetime that follows.

The basis for introducing Meducide

As part of my post graduate studies in 2026, I have conducted a scoping review titled “Destruction and reconstruction of medical education in armed conflict zones” (Forthcoming) in which I reviewed global literature published in five databases between 2004 and 2025. The scoping review identified evidence from a wide range of conflict-affected zones, including Afghanistan, Iraq, Liberia, Myanmar, Palestine, Sierra Leone, Sudan, Syria, Ukraine and more. Across these contexts, several recurring patterns emerged. These are:

- Medical education is disrupted through the destruction and militarization of infrastructure. Medical schools, laboratories, student dormitories, and teaching hospitals have been destroyed, occupied, looted, or repurposed for military or displacement-related use (Among others: Challoner & Forget, 2011; Mahgoub et al., 2024; Mayer et al., 2023).
- Collapse of clinical training is one of the central mechanisms of Meducide. Even when theoretical teaching survives through online delivery or temporary relocation, bedside teaching, procedural skills, emergency exposure under supervision, and longitudinal patient interactions are much harder or even impossible to preserve (Among others: Dobiesz et al., 2022; Fares et al., 2020).
- Conflicts erode ministries, accreditation systems, examination processes, and professional regulation. In some contexts, competing authorities emerge; in others, licensing processes are suspended, records are lost, or curricula become politically distorted. These disruptions affect recognized standards, valid assessment, and the legitimacy of qualifications (Among others: Bdaiwi et al., 2023; Stanikzai et al., 2025).
- Armed conflicts pushes educators and clinicians into migration, exile, silence, or death. Students are internally displaced, trapped by checkpoints and siege, or forced across borders without clear systems of credit recognition or transfer. These losses are intergenerational.

- Students and teachers in war zones do not learn or teach under ordinary conditions. They do so while displaced, bereaved, under bombardment, at checkpoints, or in shelters, often with significant symptoms of anxiety, depression, or post-traumatic stress which directly shape concentration, retention, ethical judgement, and professional identity formation (Among others: Alfadul et al., 2025; Omer et al., 2024)

Why Meducide matters

The significance of Meducide lies in the fact that it links the destruction of education directly to the destruction of public health and health-system futures. Global health literature has already established that workforce shortages are unequally distributed, most severe in low-resource and fragile settings, and strongly associated with reduced service coverage and poorer health outcomes (Boniol et al., 2022; Haakenstad et al., 2022). Furthermore, conflict deepens these shortages not only by killing or displacing practicing clinicians, but also by destroying the institutions that train the next generation. Therefore, medical education is not peripheral to public health recovery; it is foundational to it.

The public health consequences are immediate as well as delayed. For example, in the long term, it contributes to specialist shortages, weak faculty renewal, reduced research capacity, and deeper dependency on external actors. Rebuilding hospitals without rebuilding medical education risks producing health systems that remain institutionally fragile and professionally depleted.

Moreover, Meducide matters because it sharpens analytical and political attention. It makes it visible that attacks on medical schools are not only attacks on students or universities, but they are attacks on future care, future survival, future public and population health, and future sovereignty. Medical schools are often targeted because they are symbols of continuity, expertise, and national capacity. Therefore, attention to and naming this pattern matters for advocacy, documentation, and accountability.

Implications for protection, reconstruction, and policy

Recognizing Meducide as a concept has significant and practical implications. Medical education institutions should be protected by humanitarian and legal organizations and frameworks, because the destruction is not only an educational, but also have serious threat on the long-term populations' health and recovery. They also show that post-conflict rebuilding should go beyond physical infrastructure and include every involved body such as clinical training sites, accreditation systems, faculty development, student support, and assessment pathways. This is because medical schools cannot function without teaching hospitals and recognized routes into licensing and practice. Furthermore, the concept of Meducide highlights the need for curriculum reform so that conflict medicine, disaster response, trauma care, triage, ethics, mental health, and health-system adaptation are treated as core competencies in crisis-affected settings. The findings from part studies and the review emphasizes the importance of sustained international collaboration through digital infrastructure, diaspora engagement, faculty exchange, and cross-border recognition of study and credentials, while ensuring that local leadership remains central. Lastly, the review of the literature brings to forefront an urgent research agenda focused on graduate competence, faculty return, specialist shortages, regulation, governance, licensing, and the long-term effects of medical education destruction on health systems and population health.

Conclusion

Meducide offers a focused language for understanding how armed conflicts and wars destroy not only health services in the present, but the possibility of rebuilding health systems in the future. Inspired by wider debates on the destruction of education, it identifies medical education as a distinct and especially consequential site of attack. Medical schools are not merely academic institutions caught in conflict; they are infrastructures of care, expertise, and collective survival. Their destruction therefore deserves special conceptual, legal, and policy attention.

To name Meducide is not to invent a dramatic term for rhetorical effect. It is to achieve analytic precision. It is to recognize that the destruction of medical education is neither accidental nor secondary, but part of a wider pattern through which conflict reshapes health, inequity, and institutional fragility across generations. Therefore, protecting medical education is not only an educational duty; it is global and public health imperative.

References

- Alfadul, E. S., Alrawa, S. S. K., Hemmeda, L., Adam, A. Y. T., Mohamed Salih Mohamed Nour, S., Ebrahim Hamed Saeed, N., ... & Mustafa, A. (2025). Effect of military conflict on mental health: A cross-sectional study among the medical students at Khartoum governmental universities, Sudan, 2023. *BMJ open*, *15*(3), e086495.
- Alousi, R. (2022). Educide: the genocide of education a case study on the impact of invasion and conflict on education. *The Business and Management Review*, *13*(2), 8-9.
- Barnett-Vanes, A. (2016). Armed conflict, medical training and health systems. *Medicine, conflict and Survival*, *32*(1), 30-39.
- Barnett-Vanes, A., Hassounah, S., Shawki, M., Ismail, O. A., Fung, C., Kedia, T., ... & Majeed, A. (2016). Impact of conflict on medical education: a cross-sectional survey of students and institutions in Iraq. *BMJ open*, *6*(2), e010460.
- Bdaiwi, Y., Alchalati, S., Sabouni, A., Al-Khalil, M., Abdrabbuh, O., Kejah, A., ... & Ekzayez, A. (2023). Medical education system (re) building in a fragile setting: Northwest Syria as a case study. *PLOS Global Public Health*, *3*(4), e0001340.
- Boniol, M., Kunjumen, T., Nair, T. S., Siyam, A., Campbell, J., & Diallo, K. (2022). The global health workforce stock and distribution in 2020 and 2030: a threat to equity and 'universal' health coverage?. *BMJ global health*, *7*(6).
- Challoner, K. R., & Forget, N. (2011). Effect of civil war on medical education in Liberia. *International Journal of Emergency Medicine*, *4*(1), 6.
- Dobiesz, V. A., Schwid, M., Dias, R. D., Aiwonodagbon, B., Tayeb, B., Fricke, A., ... & Erickson, T. B. (2022). Maintaining health professional education during war: A scoping review. *Medical Education*, *56*(8), 793-804.
- Fares, J., Fares, M. Y., & Fares, Y. (2020). Medical schools in times of war: integrating conflict medicine in medical education. *Surgical neurology international*, *11*, 5.

Haakenstad, A., Irvine, C. M. S., Knight, M., Bintz, C., Aravkin, A. Y., Zheng, P., ... & Sahu, M. (2022). Measuring the availability of human resources for health and its relationship to universal health coverage for 204 countries and territories from 1990 to 2019: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019. *The Lancet*, 399(10341), 2129-2154.

Iriqat, D., Alousi, R., Aldahdouh, T. Z., AlDahdouh, A., Dankar, I., Alburai, D., ... & Hassoun, A. (2025). Educide amid conflict: the struggle of the Palestinian education system. *Quality Education for All*, 2(1), 83-101.

Mahgoub, E. A. A., Khairy, A., Osman, S., Haga, M. B., Osman, S. H. M., Abbu Hassan, A. M., ... & Babiker, A. (2024). War and education: the attacks on medical schools amidst ongoing armed conflict, Sudan 2023. *Conflict and health*, 18(1), 23.

Mayer, A., Yaremko, O., Shchudrova, T., Korotun, O., Dospil, K., & Hege, I. (2023). Medical education in times of war: a mixed-methods needs analysis at Ukrainian medical schools. *BMC medical education*, 23(1), 804.

Mayer, A., Yaremko, O., Shchudrova, T., Korotun, O., Dospil, K., & Hege, I. (2023). Medical education in times of war: a mixed-methods needs analysis at Ukrainian medical schools. *BMC medical education*, 23(1), 804.

Stanikzai, M. H., Shanawa, S., Karimkhil, A. T., & Dadras, O. (2025). Medical education in Afghanistan: challenges and policy implications. *Advances in Medical Education and Practice*, 477-482.

United Nations Human Rights Office of the High Commissioner. (2024, April 18). *UN experts deeply concerned over "scholasticide" in Gaza*. <https://www.ohchr.org/en/press-releases/2024/04/un-experts-deeply-concerned-over-scholasticide-gaza>